

Food Review Analysis Using nltk And SentimentIntencityAnalyser

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II. BASIC TERMINOLOGY USED

A. *nltk*

Abstract—There has been a large stream of user-generated information such as customer comments, opinions, and reviews since the internet's inception. Sentiment analysis on the web solves the challenge of gathering data on the internet and extracting information about people's feelings. Customer feedback may assist you in determining how people feel about a product and how it is perceived in the market. A variety of industrial programmes may be used to do sentiment analysis. In this study, we propose a technique for analysing client feedback on food products and determining whether it is good or bad. Positive, negative, and neutral are the three categories in this system, and we'll count the words and analyse the complete sentence to see which one it belongs to.

Natural language processing (NLP) is a branch of computer science that tries to help computers understand natural human language. The Natural Language Toolkit, or NLTK, is a Python package that allows you to handle natural language. The Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) is a Python programming language that may be used to create statistical natural language processing programmes that interface with human language data. It includes tokenization, parsing, categorization, stemming, tagging, and semantic reasoning text processing techniques. In our system, we use `nltk.tokenize`. This is used to create substring lists from text. Tokenizers can be used to search a string for words and punctuation..

Keywords— Customer reviews, sentiment analysis, machine learning, opinion mining, natural language processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

When making a decision, knowing "what everyone else thought" is usually helpful. On a daily basis, people argue a wide range of topics on social media sites. Information services such as online services, which link data items to offer interactive access, are provided through the Web and its associated distribution services. Because web pages may lack a standard schema or structure, computers may struggle to interpret semantic meaning. Organizations want a slice of the pie to learn how their target customers communicates and to discover the vital data that runs their business. Sentiment analysis is the automatic extraction of sentiments and opinions from material using Natural Language Processing (NLP)..

B. *wordcloud*

A word cloud is a graphical representation of text information (also known as a tag cloud or a weighted list). The font size and colour indicate the importance of the words, which are usually single words. Fortunately, Python has a wordcloud library that makes it possible to create them.

C. *VaderSentiment Analysis*

VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) is a sentiment analysis tool based on social media feelings, including a lexicon and rules. VADER employs a range of strategies. A sentiment lexicon is a collection of lexical properties (such as words) that are classified as Positive or Negative according to their semantic orientation. VADER displays the Positivity and Negativity scores, as well as the degree to which a sensation is good or bad.

The technique of categorising opinions in a piece of information or document into "positive," "negative," or "neutral" categories is known as sentiment analysis. Sentiment analysis at the document level distinguishes positive and negative sentiment by treating the entire content as a single subject. Sentence level classification is used to categorise the sentiment represented in each sentence. There isn't much of a difference between sentence and document level because sentences are part of documents. The document must be processed to the aspect level in order to acquire comprehensive views or sentiments. The goal of aspect-level sentiment analysis is to figure out what makes each aspect and target entity tick. This model is used to classify sentiment polarity. Around 1000 food reviews were acquired from Amazon for this paper's dataset. Before being published on Amazon, each post is examined and authenticated.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

In sentiment analysis, machine learning, lexicon-based, and hybrid methodologies are all employed. Machine learning techniques are utilised in supervised classification. A lexicon-based strategy necessitates the collecting of opinion terms. The term "hybrid method" refers to an approach that blends language and machine learning. Language-related computing methods are referred to as natural language processing. The majority of extant research focuses on internet-based data mining. Prior to the Internet, surveys were used to collect information or views on many topics.

In order to find negation phrases, Xing et al[2]. presented a study focused on Amazon product reviews. For data collected between February and April 2014, data is categorised at the sentence and review levels.

Fig5: Pie-chart

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

the practice of recognizing the feelings represented in a text or document is known as sentiment analysis. we suggested a score-based system for mining food reviews, which we combined with existing text analysis software. using the polarity score, the suggested system gave a very good result. Prediction-based approaches will be combined with the present methodology in future study. To handle the implicit sentiment analysis, more characteristics will be extracted.

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